

Water Quality Detection Using Machine Learning

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Abstract—Ensuring safe water quality is paramount for public health and environmental sustainability. This study investigates the use of machine learning techniques, specifically Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, to predict water potability along with recommendation based on key physicochemical parameters. Through analysis of a comprehensive dataset comprising pH, hardness, solids, chloramines, sulfate, and conductivity measurements, ensemble models are trained and evaluated for their accuracy in classifying water as potable or non-potable. Additionally, feature importance and correlations among water quality indicators are examined to provide insights into their significance. The results highlight the efficacy of machine learning in predicting water quality and offer valuable implications for water resource management and environmental protection.

Keywords: Water Quality Prediction, Machine Learning, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Physicochemical Parameters

I. INTRODUCTION

Water, a vital resource indispensable for sustaining life and ecosystems, faces ongoing challenges in maintaining its quality due to natural and human-induced factors. In this study, we explore the application of machine learning (ML) algorithms to predict water quality outcomes with heightened accuracy and efficiency.

By analyzing datasets containing key water parameters such as pH levels, hardness, solids concentration, chloramines, sulfate content, and conductivity, ML algorithms can discern complex patterns and relationships, enabling the reliable classification of water as potable or non-potable. Our focus lies on demonstrating how ML techniques, particularly Random Forest and Gradient Boosting classifiers, can be harnessed to develop predictive models for water quality assessment. The advantage of employing machine learning algorithms lies in their ability to analyze vast amounts of water quality data and extract meaningful insights with high accuracy. Through iterative refinement based on labeled data, these algorithms acquire the capability to make accurate predictions on unseen test data.

Throughout the study, we delve into the intricacies of ML model development, encompassing data preprocessing, feature selection, model training, and performance evaluation. Algorithms, such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting classifiers, offer powerful tools for predicting water quality with precision and reliability. By leveraging complex patterns in water parameter data, these algorithms can effectively classify water as potable or non-potable, aiding in informed decision-making for resource management and conservation efforts.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Nair J P & S.V M, Predictive models for river water quality using machine learning and Big Data Techniques [1]

This paper explores the utilization of sophisticated big data and machine learning methodologies to predict water quality. It delves into the analysis of time series data and discusses the application of deep learning for water quality assessment. Additionally, it addresses environmental research challenges, proposing solutions through machine learning and big data analytics. By leveraging these technologies, the paper aims to enhance water quality forecasting, thereby facilitating more efficient monitoring and management of water resources. Through a comprehensive examination of these approaches, the paper contributes to the advancement of methods for evaluating and predicting water quality in various environmental contexts.

B. Ali M, Qamar A M, Data Analysis, Quality Indexing and Prediction of Water Quality for the Management of Rawal Watershed in Pakistan [2]

Prioritizing water quality at consumption locations is essential, as downstream water sources suffer when action is neglected. Watershed management is vital for long-term water quality goals. This study examines Rawal's watershed, impacted by urbanization and deforestation, over 2009–2012. Supervised learning, particularly Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), proves more accurate for assessing water quality trends.

C. Khan Y & See C S, Predicting and analyzing water quality using machine learning a comprehensive model [3]

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This study focused on water quality characteristics including chlorophyll concentration and dissolved oxygen content, and it used artificial neural networks (ANNs) and temporal analysis to forecast the quality of the water. Four chosen water quality parameters and ANN models have been examined. Both nonlinear auto-regressive time series and artificial neural networks were used. Thus, it benefits both the accuracy and predictive aspects of water quality

D.N.S.Kavitha,M.Sakthivel,B Sreedevi,G Revathy,Water Quality Prediction Using Ensembled Machine Learning[4]

Advanced machine learning (ML) algorithms, such as supervised learning methods like Multi-Layer Perceptrons, are used in the prediction of water quality (MLP). To compute measures like the Water Quality Classification (WQC) and Water Quality Index (WQI), these algorithms examine data on water quality. They are essential to modelling and forecasting trends in water quality. Evaluation metrics that evaluate the accuracy and performance of these algorithms include Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE).

E.Gandhimathi S K; Muppagowni G K,A Proficient Prediction Mechanism for Analyzing Water Quality Using Machine Learning Algorithms [5]

Predicting water quality helps with planning pollution control strategies. The availability of drinkable water is still vital because health is so important. Water potability is a difficult concept to define, with implications for government policy and public health. To improve prediction accuracy, this study uses machine learning methods such as Random Forest, XGBoost, SVM, CNN, and RCNN. Better techniques guarantee higher-quality assessments of water quality, which is advantageous for government and public health.

III. METHODOLOGY

The main aim of this project is to predict water quality levels along with recommendation using advanced data analysis techniques, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions about water usage and safety. This methodology involves a systematic approach that integrates data collection, analysis, and predictive modeling. By leveraging machine learning algorithms and relevant water quality parameters, this system aims to provide accurate forecasts and valuable insights for effective water resource management and public health protection.

A. Data Collection:

The dataset used in this study, comprises a comprehensive collection of parameters crucial for evaluating water quality. It includes key features such as pH levels, hardness, solids concentration, chloramines, sulfate levels, and conductivity. These parameters play pivotal roles in determining the potability and safety of water for various purposes, including drinking and industrial usage.

```
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier, GradientBoostingClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
# Load the dataset
data = pd.read_csv('water_quality.csv')
```

Fig 1 : import packages

B. Data Preprocessing:

Data preprocessing encompasses tasks such as handling missing values and scaling features to prepare the dataset for analysis or modeling.

```
data.dropna(inplace=True)
```

Fig 2 : drop rows with missing values

```
relevant_features = ['ph', 'Hardness', 'Solids', 'Chloramines', 'Sulfate', 'Conductivity']
X = data[relevant_features]
y = data['Potability']
```

Fig 3: considering only relevant features

C. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA):

Involves visualizing key features of the dataset through techniques like box plots and heatmaps to understand the distribution and relationships between variables, aiding in identifying patterns and potential correlations within the data.

```
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
sns.heatmap(X.corr(), annot=True, cmap='coolwarm', fmt=".2f")
plt.title('Correlation Heatmap')
plt.show()
```

Fig 4 : creating heatmap to analyze correlation between features

Fig 5 : Heatmap

```
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
sns.boxplot(data=X)
plt.title('Boxplot of Features')
plt.show()
```

Fig 6: creating Boxplot to analyze the distribution of features

Fig 7 : Boxplot

D.Feature Selection :

Feature Selection entails identifying and retaining the most significant attributes from the dataset to enhance model accuracy and efficiency in machine learning tasks.

```
relevant_features = ['pH', 'Hardness', 'Solids', 'Chloramines', 'Sulfate', 'Conductivity']
X = data[relevant_features]
```

Fig 8 : Relevant features

E.Data Splitting :

The data is split into training and testing sets using the train_test_split function

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

Fig 9 : splitting of data

F.Model Building :

builds ensemble models using Random Forest and Gradient Boosting algorithms, fitting them on the training data to learn patterns and relationships

```
rf_model = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
gb_model = GradientBoostingClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)

# Fit the models on the training data
rf_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
gb_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

Fig 10 : creating ensemble model

G. Prediction Function :

Create a function to predict water potability

```
def predict_potability(ph, Hardness, Solids, Chloramines, Sulfate, Conductivity):
    potability_rf = rf_model.predict([[ph, Hardness, Solids, Chloramines, Sulfate, Conductivity]])[0]
    potability_gb = gb_model.predict([[ph, Hardness, Solids, Chloramines, Sulfate, Conductivity]])[0]
    return "Good to use" if (potability_rf + potability_gb) >= 1 else "Not good to use"
```

Fig 11: code for predicting water potability

A. Results :

Input Water Quality Parameters

pH value

Hardness (mg/L)

Total Solids (ppm)

Chloramines (ppm)

Sulfate (mg/L)

Conductivity (µS/cm)

Fig 12 : Output user interface

IV CONCLUSION

Water Quality Detection Using Machine Learning has focused on the application of machine learning techniques for water potability prediction and remedial recommendation. Through the utilization of Random Forest and Gradient Boosting classifiers, this study has achieved notable accuracy in forecasting water potability based on essential water quality parameters.

Water Quality detection applies machine learning to forecast water safety and recommend solutions. Using Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, it accurately predicts water quality based on essential parameters. It suggests remedies like pH adjustment and filtration to enhance water quality. Integrating machine learning into water management helps mitigate health risks from contaminated water. Ultimately, it ensures access to safe drinking water and protects public health and the environment

V REFERENCES

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Fig 13: Output result 1

Fig 14 : Output result 2

Algorithm	Accuracy
Random Forest	84%
Gradient Boosting	88%

Table 1 : Accuracies with different Algorithms

Total Accuracy: 0.88					
	precision	recall	f1-score	support	
0	0.89	0.80	0.84	20	
1	0.88	0.93	0.90	30	
accuracy			0.88	50	
macro avg	0.88	0.87	0.87	50	
weighted avg	0.88	0.88	0.88	50	

Fig 15 : Classification report

